

Comparative evaluation of major pollutants from different sites of Pakistan

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Abstract : The continuously increasing air pollution within the third world countries (such as Pakistan) is causing health related problems in the local residents. The objective of the present study is to quantify major pollutants present in the air (sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), noise level and suspended particulate matter (SPM)) as well as comparing the acquired results with the reported standard global values. The measurements of the pollutants were performed for three consecutive months ((June, July, August) 2015) at two locations namely Liaqatabad (Site 1) and Khurrianwala (Site 2); both of which are the part of Faisalabad District, Pakistan. The reason to select these two locations was the fact that the selected sites are in close proximity of main industrial area of Pakistan. Tremendous flux of population as well as continuous movement of heavy traffic vehicles on nearby National Highway and Motorway makes these locations prone to air pollution. The measured values of air quality parameters in these areas were compared with the published National and International Ambient Quality Standards (NAAQS). Among those air pollutants SO₂, SPM and noise levels were found to be significantly higher compared to NAAQS in the selected locations. However, CO concentrations were found within the permissive limits. The SO₂, CO, noise level and SPM values were recorded as 418–652 μg m⁻³, 3.03–3.44 mg m⁻³, 68–73 dB and 555–667 μg m⁻³ compared to the standard values (150 μg m⁻³, 10 mg m⁻³, 65 dB and 550 μg m⁻³) respectively. These variations among air quality parameters suggest that there is a strong need to devise effective pollution control measures for industrial areas of third world countries.

Keywords : Ambient air quality, NAAQS, air pollution, carbon monoxide, SO₂.

Introduction

According to the predictions of World Health Organization, about 2 million premature deaths occur every year in urban areas of the world due to air pollution alone¹; changing climate as well as fluctuating pattern of rain fall are the natural contributing factors in enhancement of air pollution and associated potential health hazards^{2,3}. Also, the vehicular traffic density and smoke are the major contributing factors from humans which are constantly adding gaseous pollutants and high auditory noise in the environment⁴. In this regard, the ambient air standards were devised in literature as well as detailed information has been given on Particulate Matter (PM)⁵ and gaseous emission, particularly of SO₂⁶⁻⁸.

The SO₂ is known to be a chronic gas, affecting car-

diac muscles, if inhaled, and causing lung cancer eventually. The PM as well as sulphur and nitrogen oxide-related chemicals cause cardiopulmonary mortality in human beings². The anthropogenic activities, geographical setting, city planning, design and climatology contribute primarily in the emission of air pollutants⁹. Five major known air pollutants are carbon monoxide (CO), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), ozone (O₃) and suspended particulate matter (SPM)¹⁰.

Since the last decade, there are growing concerns about pollution due to enormous population increase, urbanization and industrialization in the world. Due to the impractical approach and scarcity of monitoring techniques, developing and underdeveloped countries are constantly filling their environment up with polluted air which re-

sults in the health deterioration of the local inhabitants.

The primary focus of the present study was to assess the ambient air quality at two locations namely Khurrianwala and Liaqatabad; both of which belong to district Faisalabad, Pakistan. The reasons to choose these two places from a developing country (Pakistan) were the facts that these huge areas have poor infra-structure, a number of industries are situated nearby and these areas face higher in and out flux of heavy traffic vehicles, therefore these locations are the ideal representative sites for industrial sectors of the third world countries. This research is a better way to assess the changes occurring with the passage of time in ambient air quality and also focuses upon the standardization of these parameters according to the World Health Organization standards. For this purpose, SO₂, CO, noise level and SPM were selected as an envoy of air quality of these selected places.

Experimental

The air quality monitoring was conducted with the assistance of EPA laboratory. Mobile unit was used to collect the data. The used analytical techniques are given as under :

SO₂ measurement :

LaMotte test was used for monitoring SO₂ in air using an adjustable flow meter. Three samples were taken from each site; averaged the measurements and air calibration chart is used to convert index reading to concentration. The analytical balance (Model GR-202) was used to measure the weights of measured pollutants.

CO measurement :

Gas alert extreme device was used to measure the CO concentrations at selected sites. The “cube button” and “circle button” were pressed simultaneously and held for 5 s; the detector beeped, vibrations were produced by the instrument and after “CAL” displayed on the LCD detector, instrument produced more beeps. The LCD flashed “auto-zero” and the detector sensor reading became zero. Finally, two beeps were produced by the instrument at the end of auto zero and the LCD displayed the “current calibration gas concentration” which was recorded by pressing “accept concentration” button. Three samples

were taken from each site.

Noise level measurement :

A sound level detection meter (SESELLA CEL-6XO series) was used for measuring noise pollution at the selected experimental sites. The meter was calibrated by setting the calibration frequency at 1.0 KHz. The noise levels were recorded in triplicate at different distances from a designated center point and their mean was taken for interpretation of results.

SPM analysis in air :

Minivol portable air sampler (Model # SN : 4478) was used to measure SPM in the air of selected sites. Filter paper was loaded carefully in filtration assembly and transferred to the field site. The dust from ambient air of both sites was allowed to stick on the filter paper for the measurement of SPM. Three samples were taken from each site.

Results and discussion

The determined concentrations are briefly discussed below :

Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) :

The concentration of SO₂, at both experimental sites, was found to be 418 µg m⁻³ and 652 µg m⁻³ respectively (Fig. 1, Table 1). The concentration of SO₂ at both sites was higher than suggested limits by NAAQS. This higher concentration of SO₂ can be attributed to the untreated emissions from the nearby industries into the air; it indicates that the ambient air quality has become polluted.

Fig. 1. Comparison of SO₂ level between two experimental sites and NAAQS.

Table 1. Comparative account on reported concentrations of SO₂, CO, noise level and SPM in renowned countries of the world versus experimental sites of this study

Countries	Pollutants			
	SO ₂ (ppm/ $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	CO (ppm/ mg m^{-3})	Noise level (dB)	SPM ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
EPA limits	0.075/28.62	35/40	70	15
Europe	5/10	6/7	–	8
India	0.03/80	0.007/2.0	–	60
Bangladesh	0.03/1.45	35/40	–	150
Pakistan	0.04/40	0.003/10	–	500
Site 1	418 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	3.03 mg m^{-3}	65	667
Site 2	652 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	3.44 mg m^{-3}	73	555

According to the revised guidelines of World Health Organization regarding SO₂ emissions, the permitted lower and higher ranges were 20 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and 500 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ respectively¹¹. The concentration of SO₂ reported from global data^{12,13} in various cities of Pakistan were 52.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Islamabad, 41.9 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Rawalpindi, 57.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Faisalabad, 57.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Karachi, 57.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Peshawar and 68.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Quetta¹⁴, much higher than developed countries¹⁵.

Carbon monoxide (CO) :

The CO level was found to be 3.03 mg m^{-3} at site 1 whereas it was 3.44 mg m^{-3} at site 2 (Fig. 2). Although the concentration of CO at both locations was within the permitted limits, the monitored values are still an alarming matter for near future because measured concentrations were considerably higher in comparison to previous reported data on this subject². Even minor increase in

Fig. 2. Comparison of CO level between two experimental sites and NAAQS.

CO concentration is known as hazardous not only for human health but also for wild life. In the year 2012, reported CO range is 10.4–11.5 mg m^{-3} in Karachi, 2.1 mg m^{-3} in Rawalpindi and 1.8 mg m^{-3} in Islamabad¹⁴. In another study, the reported concentrations are as follows : Quetta (16.1 mg m^{-3}), Karachi (5.8 mg m^{-3}), Rawalpindi (4.6 mg m^{-3}), Islamabad and Peshawar (3.5 mg m^{-3} each). According to literature, the CO standard value in Tennessee and Australia is 10.3 mg m^{-3} (9 ppm); above this concentration CO would be extremely toxic for human health¹⁶.

Noise level :

Noise pollution is also categorized as a serious environmental problem in industrial areas of developing and underdeveloped countries. The selected site 2 has an industrial as well as residential sector; the average noise levels measured at both sites were 73 dB and 68 dB, respectively. At both sites, the noise level was found to be violating the NAAQS (70 dB) noise level limit (Table 1). This higher noise level is due to in and out flux of heavy traffic vehicles in these experimental sites (Fig. 3). According to literature, the noise level in Europe is higher than 70 dB as well¹⁷. The exposure of human beings to a noise level higher than 70 dB can cause deafness as traffic noise is a second serious threat for hearing loss¹⁸. In India reported noise was 72.48 dB, the main cause of which was again higher bulk of vehicular traffic¹⁹.

Fig. 3. Comparison of noise level between two experimental sites and NAAQS.

Suspended particulate matter (SPM) :

Suspended particulate matter refers to small solid and liquid aerosols of all shapes, sizes and compositions²⁰. The measured concentrations of SPM at site 1 and site 2 were 667 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and 555 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Comparison of SPM between two experimental sites and NAAQS.

The SPM contents at both sites were found to be significantly higher as compared to NAAQS permitted limits ($15 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) devised by Environmental Protection Agency and World Health Organization in 2014. These measured values of SPM were also found higher than various other maintained standards worldwide such as Chinese air quality secondary standard limits ($200 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), Hong Kong ($80 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), Chinese air quality tertiary standard limits ($300 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), USEPA National Ambient Air Quality Standards ($50 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and for European Commission Ambient Air Quality Standards ($30 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)²¹. These values were also found higher as compared to previously reported values for other big cities in Pakistan (Islamabad, Karachi, Lahore, Peshawar, Quetta and Rawalpindi; 188, 194, 202, 250 and 191 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively) as well as other countries such as Bangkok (Thailand) $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Singapore $31 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Tokyo (Japan) $30 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Busan (South Korea) $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Seoul (South Korea) $61 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Daegu (South Korea) $58 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Incheon (South Korea) $62 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Jakarta (Indonesia) $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Manila (Philippines) $40 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Hanoi (Vietnam) $112 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Shanghai (China) $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Kathmandu (Nepal) $129 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Colombo (Sri Lanka) $80 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Dhaka (Bangladesh) $131 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and Kolkata (India) $122 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ ²²⁻²⁴. The $160\text{--}506 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ PM was calculated in rainy season in Faisalabad city, Pakistan. It was quite low when compare with NAAQS permitted limits²². The ambient air quality study was conceded out for 24 h in Madhya Pradesh, India²⁵. The average values of SO_2 , NO_x and PM were always further than the permissible limits²⁶.

The comparative account on reported pollutant concentrations particularly SO_2 , CO, noise level and SPM in developed countries (USA and Europe), developing coun-

tries (India, Bangladesh and Pakistan) and at experimental sites of this study is given (Table 1). The concentration of SO_2 pollutant in USA is reported to be very close to the permissive limit, $28.62 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ calculated by United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). Europe has quite low concentration of SO_2 range ($5\text{--}10 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) compared to USA due to higher vegetation, ideal climate conditions, low population growth, use of environment friendly vehicles and properly managed industrial wastes whereas the concentration of SO_2 is reported quite high in developing countries; Bangladesh ($11.45 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), Pakistan ($40 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and India ($80 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) in literature. The SO_2 concentration in experimental site 1 and 2 was found to be $418 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $652 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively which is alarmingly high due to presence of various industries and heavy vehicular traffic in these areas. The ISO certification of industries as well as proper vehicle maintenance records at government level may lead towards the reduction of SO_2 concentration in the environment.

Conclusions

This experimental research revealed that the concentrations of SO_2 , CO, SPM and noise level at the selected sites in the third world were beyond the permitted limits. The contents of SO_2 , CO, SPM and noise level were found quite high as compared to permitted limits (NAAQS and USEPA). This prevailing condition can be more worrying due to dry weather conditions, rapid industrialization and uncontrolled population size. Pakistan is a developing country, having inadequate resources and least trained manpower to monitor the ambient air quality at regular basis. The environmental agencies should start environment friendly programs in order to control, protect and clean the ambient air quality to provide a healthy and prosperous life to the inhabitants.

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